

Grain yield had high positive significant association with all of the characters except filled grains of secondary branches, chaffy grains of primary branches, and total chaffy grains (see table). Among the panicle traits, total filled grains, primary length, and secondary length showed both positive association as well as direct effect on yield. Number of secondary branches and panicle length had significant positive

correlation with yield, but they exhibited negative direct effect on yield.

The indirect effects of panicle length, number of primary and secondary branches, primary length, secondary length, and number of filled grains of primary branches through total filled grains were found to be very high and positive. Number of filled grains of secondary branches had a negative direct effect on yield and negative correlation

with yield, while secondary length had a positive correlation with yield.

Filled grain should be emphasized because of high positive correlations, very high direct effects, and positive indirect effects on yield through many traits. Plant type for high yield in rice should have lengthy panicles, a high number of filled grains, and long primary and secondary branches. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Geographical distribution of varieties resistant to rice tungro disease (RTD)

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A rice viruses data base (RVDB), developed at IRRI in 1990, organizes information about resistance to RTD, rice ragged stunt virus, and rice grassy stunt virus. The system enables researchers to access current information about rice accessions that have been evaluated for virus resistance and are stored in the International Rice Germplasm Center (IRGC).

Analysis of the updated data for RTD resistance in the RVDB showed that 15,795 accessions (20.5% of the IRGC collection) had been tested before 1989 for RTD resistance as infection rate. Among them, 560 (3.5%) are resistant (less than 30% infection).

Most of the resistant varieties originated in South Asia, particularly in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan (see table). Of the 273 resistant varieties from India, 259 were ARC lines; 32 of the 63 varieties from Pakistan were Basmati lines. Although the percentage of resistant accessions from Indonesia is low, some important resistant varieties, such as Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, and Balimau Putih, originated in this country.

We used the mass screening method to evaluate untested varieties originating from Bangladesh, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. Of the 3,656 accessions tested, 355 (9.5%) are resistant to RTD. The results show that a higher percentage of

resistant materials was obtained when mass screening was concentrated on varieties originating from a particular

Frequency count of accessions resistant to RTD, by geographical region.

Origin	Tested (no.)	Resistant	
		no.	%
1963-89			
East Asia	946	4	0.4
Southeast Asia	5,274	52	1.0
Cambodia	63	0	0.0
Indonesia	1,517	25	1.6
Laos	753	0	0.0
Malaysia	361	7	1.9
Myanmar	811	2	0.2
Philippines	878	10	1.1
Thailand	393	2	0.5
Vietnam	497	6	1.2
South Asia	7,590	490	6.5
Bangladesh	2,956	149	5.0
Bhutan	33	0	0.0
India	3,101	273	8.8
Nepal	40	1	2.5
Pakistan	758	63	8.3
Sri Lanka	702	4	0.6
West Asia	125	3	2.4
Africa	1,275	9	0.7
South America	161	0	0.0
North and Central America	226	1	0.4
Oceania	20	0	0.0
Europe	27	0	0.0
Unknown	151	1	0.7
Total	15,795	560	3.5
1990-91			
South Asia			
Bangladesh	2,150	263	12.2
Pakistan	283	18	6.4
Sri Lanka	1,223	79	6.5
Total	3,656	360	9.8

country of origin rather than on varieties at random.

Evaluation of untested varieties originating from India and Indonesia is in progress. ■

Effect of plant age on IR-BB21 resistance to *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo)

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Genetic resistance is the most effective and economic means of controlling bacterial blight (BB) of rice caused by Xoo. The dominant resistance locus *Xa-21* was identified in the wild rice *Oryza longistaminata*, and the near-isogenic line IR-BB21 was generated by introducing this locus into IR24. This locus was previously reported to confer resistance to all Philippine races of Xoo. We evaluated the ability of the *Xa-21* locus to confer resistance to the BB pathogen in both seedlings and adult rice plants.

Seeds at two stages during the development of IR-BB21 (GSK80 and IR-BB21) were collected on two occasions to ensure cultivar authenticity. IR-BB10 (carrying *Xa-10*), IR-BB21 (carrying *Xa-21*), and IR24 were grown in the greenhouse at about 30/25 °C (day/night) temperatures.

Strains PXO99A (azacytidine-resistant derivative of PXO99, race 6) and PXO86 (race 2) of the Philippine Xoo isolate were grown for 48 h in terrific broth, a bacterial culture medium used for

Table 1. Reaction of 14-d-old rice seedlings to infiltration with *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains.

Cultivar	Reaction ^a	
	PXO99A	PXO86
IR-BB10	W	HR
IR-BB21	W	W
IR24	W	W

^aW = water soaking, HR = hypersensitive reaction.

Table 2. Length of lesions induced by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* strains on adult rice plants 15 d after inoculation.

Cultivar	Plant age (d)	Lesion length ^a (cm)	
		PXO99A	PXO86
IR-BB10	45	14.3 a	1.0 b
IR-BB10	60	14.9 a	1.9 b
IR-BB21	45	1.4 b	2.3 b
IR-BB21	60	2.2 b	2.7 b
IR24	45	14.1 a	12.8 a
IR24	60	13.8 a	14.2 a

^aIn the same column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly ($P=0.01$) different according to Fisher's protected LSD.

growing certain strains of *E. coli*. It contains (per liter) 12 g bacto tryptone, 24 g yeast extract, 4 ml glycerol, 2.31 g KH_2PO_4 , and 12.5 g KH_2PO_4 . Cells were collected by centrifugation and resuspended in sterile water to obtain an inoculum concentration of 10^8 cfu/ml.

Fifteen plants of each cultivar were inoculated with strain PXO86 or strain PXO99A. Adult plants were inoculated at 45 or 60 d after seeding (DAS) using the leaf-clip method. Seedlings were inoculated at 14 DAS using the leaf-clip method or by localized infiltration of bacteria into leaves.

Plant reaction to Xoo was measured 4 d after inoculation (DAI) for seedlings. Susceptibility is indicated by water soaking reaction and resistance by hypersensitive reaction. Reactions of adult plants were assessed by measuring lesion length 15 DAI for 20 leaf samples per cultivar-strain combination. All experiments were conducted at least twice.

All cultivars at the seedling stage were susceptible to strain PXO99A, and IR-BB21 and IR24 were susceptible to strain PXO86 (Table 1). A hypersensitive

resistance response was observed on IR-BB10 inoculated with PXO86.

Lesion lengths on IR24 adult plants inoculated with PXO99A or PXO86 were typical of those for a susceptible reaction (Table 2). Lesion lengths on IR-BB10 inoculated with PXO99A were similar to those on IR24, but lesions induced by PXO86 on IR-BB10 were significantly shorter than those on IR24. Lesions induced by either Xoo race on adult plants

of IR-BB21 were significantly shorter than those observed on susceptible IR24 (Table 2).

Adult rice plants resistant to Xoo have markedly shorter lesions than do susceptible cultivars. These results indicate that the *Xa-21* resistance locus confers adult plant resistance to Xoo, but seedlings containing this locus are not appreciably resistant to the BB pathogen. ■

Virus detection in varieties resistant to tungro (RTD)

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Rice varieties Utri Merah (IRGC 16680) and Balimau Putih (IRGC 17204) do not show clear RTD symptoms even if infected. We traced the infection of rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) in inoculated plants by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for 5 wk. Varieties TKM6 (resistant to RTSV), Gam Pai 30-12-15 (resistant to vector), and TN1 (susceptible) served as checks.

About 80 plants/variety were planted individually in clay pots, enclosed in mylar cages, and inoculated at 21 d

after sowing using 5 *Nephotettix virescens* adults/plant for a 24-h inoculation access time. We took a 4-cm-long sample weekly from the 2d or 3d youngest expanded leaf of each plant. The samples were homogenized in 0.1 M phosphate buffer containing 0.14 M NaCl and 0.05% tween 20 at 10× dilution. Samples were tested following the normal ELISA procedure.

Utri Merah and Balimau Putih had a relatively high RTBV infection at 1 wk after inoculation (WAI). We detected RTBV in some plants only at 2 WAI; later, RTBV became undetectable in these infected plants (see table). The concentration of RTBV examined by ELISA was always lower in these varieties than in other varieties.

Detection of RTBV in some rice varieties by ELISA at 5 weekly intervals after inoculation (WAI).

Detection pattern of RTBV in individual plants ^a at given WAI					Plants (no.) showing detection pattern in				
1	2	3	4	5	Balimau Putih	Utri Merah	TKM6	Gam Pai 30-12-15	TN1
+	+	+	+	+	2	0	28	7	78
-	+	+	+	+	0	0	48	37	0
-	-	+	+	+	0	0	1	9	2
+	-	-	-	-	40	45	0	0	0
+	+	-	-	-	16	7	0	0	0
+	+	+	-	-	1	0	0	0	0
+	-	+	-	-	1	0	0	0	0
+	-	-	-	+	1	0	0	0	0
+	+	+	-	+	1	0	0	0	0
-	+	-	-	-	8	5	0	0	0
-	-	-	-	-	8	23	2	27	0
Total					79	80	79	80	80

^a+ = positive detection and - = negative detection in individual plants at each WAI. For example, ++ --- means that RTBV was detected at 1 and 2 WAI, but not at 3-5 WAI in the same plant.